

Ultra Compact Eleven-Level Single-Phase Stacked T-Type Inverter Enabled by a Solid-State Multi-Terminal Bidirectional Switch

Theofilos Moraitis

*Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Patras
Patras, Greece
t.moraitis@ac.upatras.gr*

Georgios Kampitsis

*Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Patras
Patras, Greece
gkampitsis@upatras.gr*

Abstract—Multi-level inverters have increasingly gathered interest over the past decade due to their increased efficiency and power density for demanding applications such as power generation from renewable energy sources and high-performance drive and traction systems. For lower power systems in the kW range, gate driving circuitry can occupy area and volume much larger than that of the semiconductor devices, which is especially challenging in high device count topologies, thus prohibiting increase in power density. In an attempt to minimize such circuitry, this paper proposes an implementation of an 11-level single phase inverter, which can be extended to N-levels, with minimal driving requirements in terms of signal and power isolation. The concept is then validated through an 850 W laboratory prototype, reaching a peak efficiency of 97.1% and power density of over 4 kW/L.

Index Terms—Bidirectional switch, four-quadrant switch, high power density, multi-level inverters, single-phase inverters, T-Type inverter

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric energy demand is forecast to be rapidly growing in the coming years [1]: widespread adoption of large language model chatbots such as ChatGPT and cloud services have caused an exponential increase in datacenter processing power, requiring additional facilities and thus more energy [2]. Additionally, with the quadruple increase of global electric car sales in 2024 compared to 2020 [3], it is quite evident that producing and processing energy in an efficient manner is becoming ever more important in order to accommodate the increasing load of the power grid.

Renewable energy sources (RES) have been the preferred choice in the past decade to easily increase grid capacity, while maintaining an environmentally friendly footprint [4]. Solar in particular, has seen tremendous adoption increase due to low cost and ease of installation compared to other RES, both in residential and utility scale [5]. In the very heart of solar energy conversion, lies the DC/AC converter (inverter) whose efficiency plays a large role in overall system

performance. Alongside efficiency, size is becoming more and more important: smaller and lighter inverters are associated with easier transportation, installation and maintenance, bringing overall system cost down for producers and consumers [6], [7].

Multi-level inverters (MLI) have been used extensively in the past decade to enhance efficiency and power density: from the mega-watt scale utility, propulsion and medium voltage drive inverters all the way down to the roof-top commercial building scale [8]–[10], these structures have successfully reduced the size of passive components, and especially magnetics. A shift towards capacitor based multi-level structures has also been an effective way of decreasing the volumetric footprint of converters, as they can offer orders of magnitude higher energy and gravimetric density when compared to magnetics [11].

For lower power, highly compact MLIs, an issue that is less frequently talked about is that of the massive signal and power isolation requirements for the gate driving in topologies that have an increased amount of controlled semiconductor switches. As semiconductor technology continues improving and devices can fit into smaller and smaller packages, the size of a conventional gate driving circuit can span area and volume much larger than the semiconductor itself, with the main pain-point being the isolated DC/DC converter required to power the signal isolator and gate drive integrated circuits (ICs). Cleverer solutions, like cascading bootstrap circuits, bootstrapping during deadtime or charge pump circuits have been utilized in some topologies like the flying capacitor MLI to further enhance power density and compactness [12]. Nevertheless, even these circuits require a few extra components (like voltage regulators and diodes or transistors for synchronous bootstrapping) and remove some degree of freedom from the designer, such as the ability to apply a negative voltage during turn-off or the utilization of asymmetrical duty cycles.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to revisit the 11-level variant of a generalized single phase multilevel concept first proposed in [13], shown in Fig. 1 (a), and combine it with a novel solid-state multi-terminal bidirectional switch (MTBDS) concept described in [14] and shown in Fig. 1 (b), to showcase an N-level capable and scalable single-phase MLI with minimal

Funded by the European Union (ERC grant: ENRICH, Grant Agreement 101115709, DOI 10.3030/101115709). Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Fig. 1. (a) Proposed eleven-level single-phase stacked T-type inverter and (b) multi-terminal bidirectional switch implementation and operating principles.

gate driving signal and power isolation requirements.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. The fundamentals of the topology with the proposed bidirectional switch (BDS) are discussed in Section II. Validation of the proposed concept via simulation and an 850 W laboratory hardware prototype are featured in Section III. The paper then concludes in Section IV with a concise summary and discussion of the work presented, as well as future challenges and opportunities.

II. INVERTER STRUCTURE & OPERATING PRINCIPLES

A. MTBDS Cell Operation

Before analyzing the inverter operation itself, a brief overview of a single MTBDS cell will be given. As shown in Fig. 1 (b), each cell is comprised of an n-channel device (M_{Ni}), a p-channel device (M_{Pi}) and two diodes connected in series with the FETs (D_{Ni} and D_{Pi}). The n- and p- channel branches are responsible for forward and reverse conduction, respectively. More specifically, by applying a positive gate bias to M_{Ni} , the cell acts as a diode with its "anode" connected to the drain of the device, whilst its "cathode" acts as the source. If a negative gate bias is applied to the p-channel FET, the diode is reversed. Finally, if both FETs are turned on, the cell acts as a true BDS, allowing current conduction in both directions. Full analysis of an MTBS cell can be found in [14].

B. Output Voltage States

The examined eleven-level inverter is comprised of a capacitor voltage divider (capacitors $C_1 - C_5$), a stacked T-type array of BDS $S_1 - S_4$, which forms the MTBDS, and a full-bridge cell of MOSFETs, S_+ , S_- , S_0 and S_5 . Switches $S_0 - S_5$ are responsible for changing the voltage level of node v_a , while the remaining half-bridge leg with switches S_+ and S_- is responsible for changing the polarity of the output voltage. A detailed illustration of the converter's equivalent circuits during operation is presented in Fig. 2. Finally, it is

Fig. 2. Converter equivalent circuits for output voltage v_{ab} states: (a) $+v_{dc}$, (b) $+\frac{4}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (c) $+\frac{3}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (d) $+\frac{2}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (e) $+\frac{1}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (f) $+0$, (g) -0 , (h) $-\frac{1}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (i) $-\frac{2}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (j) $-\frac{3}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, (k) $-\frac{4}{5} \cdot v_{dc}$, and (l) $-v_{dc}$. Note that for each capacitor, its state (charging or discharging) is indicated by an upwards (charging) or downwards (discharging) arrow, with blue and orange colors, respectively.

worth mentioning that for all output voltage levels except zero, there are no redundant switching states.

It can be observed that complementary states in terms of the charging and discharging of the capacitors exist during the positive and negative half-cycles, therefore providing the potential of being balanced via a single source. However, as the complementary states of the charging and discharging capacitors are associated with different absolute values of output voltage level (for example, $+0.8 \cdot V_{dc}$ and $-0.2 \cdot V_{dc}$ shown in Fig. 2 (b) and (i) respectively), non-standard pulse width modulation (PWM) schemes are required, like the ones described in [15] and [16] to balance a 7-level variant of this topology. For the scope of this paper, each capacitor is powered by a separate DC voltage source or DC/DC converter, as the capacitor balancing remains outside the scope of this work and will be addressed in the future.

C. Device Voltage Stress

With a more careful examination of Fig. 2, it is immediately noticeable that the voltage stress across the various switches is not the same. The four FETs that comprise the H-bridge are required to block the full DC-link voltage: node voltage v_a can fluctuate from 0 to v_{dc} with $0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$ increments, while node voltage v_b can be either 0 or v_{dc} .

The same cannot be said for BDS $S_1 - S_4$: while they do share a common terminal at the switching node, their other power terminal remains at a steady voltage, if capacitor ripple is sufficiently small. Additionally, each of the n- and p- parallel branches of a MTBDS cell are associated with blocking a different positive and negative voltage.

For example, switch S_1 has to be able to block at most $-0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$ during the positive half-cycle, when switch S_5 is conducting. During the negative half cycle, the maximum positive voltage stress on S_1 is limited to $+0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$, which happens when switch S_0 is conducting. Since the n-channel MOSFET (M_N) of switch S_1 is responsible for blocking positive voltages in that branch, the maximum voltage it has to withstand is limited to $+0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$. Its series connected diode (D_N) on the other hand, responsible for blocking negative voltages, needs to have a maximum blocking voltage of at least $-0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$. This is mirrored for the p-branch: the maximum voltage applied to the p-channel FET (M_P) is $-0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$, while its series connected diode (D_P) only needs withstand $+0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$. By extending this logic to the rest of the switches, their maximum voltage stress and their components are shown in detail in Table I.

The asymmetry in the voltage stress of each MTBDS cell and its comprising devices can be advantageous, since cheaper lower rated devices can be utilized, with the trade-off of an increased bill of materials. It can also be noted that while switches $S_0 - S_5$ need to block a different maximum voltage, their commutation towards conduction always happens when they block a maximum voltage of $\pm 0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$, leading to reduced switching losses. When the switches block and their voltage changes, the only energy losses that occur are attributed to the charging and discharging of the switch equivalent capacitance C_{sw} . Additionally, no large voltage overshoot should occur

TABLE I
THEORETICAL DEVICE BLOCKING VOLTAGE PARAMETERS

Switch	Component	Pos. Block. Voltage	Neg. Block. Voltage
S_0	M_N	v_{dc}	—
S_1	M_N	$+0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
	D_N	—	$-0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$
	M_P	—	$-0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$
	D_P	$+0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
S_2	M_N	$+0.4 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
	D_N	—	$-0.6 \cdot v_{dc}$
	M_P	—	$-0.6 \cdot v_{dc}$
	D_P	$+0.4 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
S_3	M_N	$+0.6 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
	D_N	—	$-0.4 \cdot v_{dc}$
	M_P	—	$-0.4 \cdot v_{dc}$
	D_P	$+0.6 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
S_4	M_N	$+0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
	D_N	—	$-0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$
	M_P	—	$-0.2 \cdot v_{dc}$
	D_P	$+0.8 \cdot v_{dc}$	—
S_5	M_N	v_{dc}	—
S_+	M_N	v_{dc}	—
S_-	M_N	v_{dc}	—

between commutation towards blocking different voltages: no current is conducted through the switch, and therefore any stray inductance cannot cause a voltage spike. Thus, it is theorized that little safety margin can be applied when rating the voltage of the devices used.

D. Gate Driving

The gate driving scheme of this topology is presented in Fig. 3. It is a combination of a phase-disposition sinusoidal pulse width modulation scheme (PD-SPWM) [17] for the switches $S_0 - S_5$, allowing for standard half-bridge driving logic, and a line frequency PWM scheme with 50% duty cycle for the S_+ and S_- switches. It is important to note the effect of dead-time

Fig. 3. Phase disposition sinusoidal pulse width modulation driving scheme (with low carrier frequency for clarity) used to drive the 11-level stacked T-type MLI.

in this topology: the MTBDS cells $S_1 - S_4$ do not create a freewheeling path when turned off. As a result, the load will be short-circuited during the dead-time duration of the positive and negative half-cycles, via the paths $S_0 - Z_L - S_+$ (positive half-cycle) and $S_5 - Z_L - S_-$ (negative half-cycle). This is also displayed in Fig. 4 (a) and (b) respectively. If the dead-time duration is too large, the inverter output voltage v_{ab} can be seriously distorted, as the voltage would drop to zero for a brief moment in every switching period. Therefore, it is crucial to minimize deadtime, while also making sure that no-shoot through of the serially connected capacitors $C_1 - C_5$ occurs. Finally, if all the switches of the inverter are turned off, which is mandatory when changing the polarity of the output voltage, depending on the direction of the current, the inverter output voltage can be either $+v_{dc}$ or $-v_{dc}$, as shown in Fig. 4 (c) and (d), respectively.

The biggest advantage of the gate driving in this topology is its practical implementation: the FETs that comprise switches $S_1 - S_4$ all share a common source. As such, only a single isolated gate driver supply is required, and multi-input signal isolators (such as digital isolators) can be employed to minimize the driving circuitry. Additionally, since there can be at most two devices conducting, the wattage of the isolated gate driver supply can be relatively small. This is also the case for the N-level generalized version of this converter. Lastly, it is important to mention that since each of the switches $S_1 - S_4$ contain two controlled devices (an n-channel and a p-channel FET), two gate driving ICs are necessary to control each FET. For the other switches, signal and power isolation is not as much of a concern: switches S_0 and S_+ are at ground potential, and a bootstrap circuit can be used to drive switches S_5 and S_- , respectively. However, as previously mentioned, using a bootstrap driving scheme removes the ability to bias the gate with a negative voltage during turn off.

Fig. 4. Dead-time states of the 11-level stacked T-type inverter: (a) in the positive half-cycle, (b) in the negative half-cycle, (c) during positive to negative polarity shift and (d) during negative to positive polarity shift.

III. SIMULATION & EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

A. Simulation

To validate the operating principles of the inverter and particularly, the voltage stress on the semiconductor devices, simulation (ideal) was carried out in MATLAB-Simulink.

The voltage stress of the various devices, synchronized with the output current for the 11-level stacked T-type inverter are shown in Fig. 5, with a bus voltage v_{dc} of 185 V. The modulation index, m_a was set to 0.98 with a 75Ω load. Connected to each phase a and b, is an inductor of $30 \mu H$ to provide some current smoothing, while also maintaining a power factor of almost one ($\cos\phi > 0.9999$). The switching frequency is 30 kHz, and the reference sine frequency is set to 60 Hz.

The maximum positive and negative blocking voltages of each switch, as discussed in Section II is confirmed by Fig. 5 (b) - (i). As also mentioned previously, each switch commutates towards conduction only when blocking a fraction of the DC bus voltage, therefore reducing the switching losses compared to other inverter topologies that switch the full DC bus with fewer devices. With the agreement of theoretical analysis and simulation, hardware verification of the proposed inverter concept can begin.

B. Hardware Prototype

To provide the final validation of the proposed inverter topology, the hardware prototype in Fig. 6 was developed. It is comprised of two printed circuit boards (PCB): a control - driver board, displayed on Fig. 6 (a), and a power board, displayed on Fig. 6 (b), which contains all the power elements, such as the DC-link capacitors, the main switching elements as well as the output filter inductors. The full assembly of the

Fig. 5. Simulation waveforms at 200 W output: (a) load current and switch voltages: (b) S_0 , (c) S_1 , (d) S_2 , (e) S_3 , (f) S_4 , (g) S_5 , (h) S_+ and (i) S_- .

Fig. 6. (a) Control and gate drive PCB, (b) power PCB containing all of the switches and output filter and (c) full-converter assembly, with heatsink installed.

converter, with its heatsink, is shown in Fig. 6 (c). The entire converter is sized at 12cm x 7cm x 2.5cm (210 mL) with the heatsink included. The most critical components of the design are listed in Table II.

For the gate driving circuitry, three isolated driver supplies were chosen to provide the desired references. As mentioned in Section II, only one of them is necessary: the other references can be provided by tying the digital reference potential to the power circuit reference potential: however it is usually good practice to isolate power and digital circuitry, in order to decouple as much noise as possible. As for the last isolated gate driver supply, providing the reference for switch S_- , it was determined that one less DC/DC converter would minimally impact the converter size and volume, and therefore it was chosen over a bootstrap circuit.

As far as the power circuit design is concerned, a crucial aspect is to match the on-state characteristics of the devices responsible for the positive and negative current: a strong mismatch between on state resistance would cause a large

difference between the forward voltage drops and thus create a DC offset in the output voltage. As shown in Table II, a good match was secured for all devices, except the 100 V NMOS and PMOS devices, which have a significant difference in $R_{DS,on}$. Nevertheless, since both of their on-state resistance is quite low, diode forward voltage dominated overall switch voltage drop, with no significant DC offset ($< 40mV$) observed in the output voltage.

C. Experimental Validation

To test the designed prototype, 5 mains isolated DC power supplies were used (ITECH IT6723H) in order to prevent capacitors $C_1 - C_5$ from discharging. All the current measurements were taken with 100 MHz current probes (Hioki 3276), and to measure all the voltage waveforms shown in this section, 25 MHz differential probes (Pico TA057) were used. All the measurements were performed on a 200 MHz, 12-bit oscilloscope (Siglent SDS1204X HD).

To start the validation process of the converter via the developed hardware, the voltages across all the switches are shown in Fig. 7 at light load conditions (200 W) and nominal DC bus voltage (185 V), without the output filter capacitor C_f for additional clarity between output current and voltage states of the switches. The inserted dead-time (50 ns) in the PWM pulses have minimal impact on the output voltage and current waveforms. Additionally, any voltage overshoot shown in Fig. 7, happens only when switches commute towards blocking after conducting, and is largely attributed to the large measurement inductance that could not be avoided as there was no direct measurement access to the power PCB. When the switches commute towards blocking a higher voltage, no overshoot is observed, since no current is conducted to cause a voltage spike through the stray inductance. Thus, it can be concluded that the assumption in Section II has been verified.

Continuing to assess the inverter's performance, full power tests were conducted with switching frequencies of 30 kHz, 60 kHz and 90 kHz. The experiments were performed by first raising the DC voltage up to its nominal 185 V, and then gradually reducing the load while monitoring the input and output currents and voltages. The resulting waveforms, for a light load of 200 W and the nominal 850 W load are shown in Fig. 8. Clearly visible are the spikes on the inverter voltage switching waveforms v_{ab} at the zero-crossing, which are

TABLE II
PROTOTYPE INVERTER MAIN COMPONENTS

Board	Component	Part Number / Value	
Control	Microcontroller	STM32F446RE	
	Gate Driver IC	1EDI20N12A x 12 (12V, 10A)	
	Iso. DC/DC Conv.	NKA0512SC x 3	
Power	$C_1 - C_5$	$11 \times 10 \mu F$ (100 V) X7R MLCC	
	L_a, L_b	$3 \times 10 \mu H$	
	C_f	$3 \times 2.2 \mu F$ (400 V) X6S MLCC	
	S_5, S_0, S_+, S_-	SQM10250E (250 V / 30 mΩ)	
	S_4	M_{N4}	IRF640NS (200 V / 150 mΩ)
		M_{P4}	SUM55P06-19L (60 V / 20 mΩ)
		D_{N4}	STPS20M60 (60 V / 20 A)
		D_{P4}	STPS20200CG (200 V / 20 A)
	S_3	M_{N3}	FDB2552 (150 V / 36 mΩ)
		M_{P3}	IXTA52P10P (100 V / 50 mΩ)
		D_{N3}	STPS30SM100S (100 V / 30 A)
		D_{P3}	STPS20150CG (150 V / 20 A)
	S_2	M_{N2}	IPB035N10 (100 V / 3.5 mΩ)
		M_{P2}	IXTA36P15P (150 V / 110 mΩ)
		D_{N2}	STPS20150CG (150 V / 20 A)
		D_{P2}	STPS30SM100S (100 V / 30 A)
	S_1	M_{N1}	IRLZ44NS (55 V / 22 mΩ)
		M_{P1}	IXTA26P20P (200 V / 170 mΩ)
		D_{N1}	STPS20200CG (200 V / 20 A)
		D_{P1}	STPS20M60 (60 V / 20 A)
	Heatsink		12cm x 7cm x 0.8cm Al. Extrusion

Fig. 7. Experimental waveforms at 200 W output: (a) load current and switch voltages: (b) S_0 , (c) S_1 , (d) S_2 , (e) S_3 , (f) S_4 , (g) S_5 , (h) S_+ and (i) S_- .

Fig. 8. Experimental output waveforms for switching frequencies of 30 kHz (a, b), 60 kHz (c, d), and 90 kHz (e, f), at power levels of 200 W (left column) and 850 W (right column).

associated with imperfections in the polarity shifting sequence of the implementation, which was implemented as follows:

- First, all of the bidirectional switches are turned off. Once disabled, the available conduction path defaults to the 0 V path for positive and negative polarities, as described previously in Fig. 4 (a) and (b) for the positive and negative half-cycles, respectively.

- Next, all the H-bridge FETs are turned off. The only available conduction path is now through their body diodes, as shown in Fig. 4 (c) and (d) for negative and positive current polarity, respectively.
- Immediately afterwards, the polarity switch (S_- or S_+) is turned on. This forces the voltage to become zero, as the conduction paths described on the first step are active.
- Finally, the PWM pulses are applied to the bidirectional switches and the H-bridge switching FETs, restoring the proper output voltage level generation.

As this procedure is executed sequentially with a microcontroller, it takes approximately 200 ns to complete. In that duration, ringing is observed at the zero-crossing as the current commutates between three states in rapid succession. While this has a minimal impact on the load voltage and current waveforms, future work shall focus on minimizing the duration of the aforementioned procedure using parallel execution.

Another noteworthy mention is the fact that asymmetric voltage dips can be observed during the positive and negative half-cycles. This is associated with the different dynamic characteristics of the N-channel and P-channel FETs that are used in the BDS $S_1 - S_4$. The dips themselves, are caused by the dead time (50 ns) between pulses, which causes a short on the load as described in Section II.

For the light and nominal load conditions of the converter and for all the range of frequencies tested, the inverter voltage v_{ab} spectrum is presented in Fig. 9. Despite the half-cycle deviations in the inverter voltage waveform, the total harmonic distortion (THD) between light and nominal load is small (below 1%). The increase of THD at higher loads can also be attributed to the increased input capacitor voltage ripple, which is increased at elevated power levels.

To conclude the experimental verification of the proposed inverter concept, the efficiency curve of the converter across a variety of resistive loads and the aforementioned frequencies is presented in Fig. 10. The efficiency was calculated by taking into account measurements from the oscilloscope, the indication of the input DC power supplies and digital multi-meters. The inverter reached a peak efficiency of 97.15%, exceeding a peak power density of 4 kW/L, and was more than 95% efficiency at the nominal load for switching frequencies of 30 kHz and 60 kHz, whilst dipping slightly below that for 90 kHz. What is even more interesting is the fact that with an increase of 300% in the switching frequency, only about a 35% increase of power losses are observed, on average. Thus, it can be deduced that the conduction losses dominate overall converter losses. All in all, the performance of the inverter is quite good, considering that its size is smaller than that of a conventional smartphone.

IV. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this work, an 11-level single-inverter stacked T-type topology is investigated, which minimizes signal and power isolation gate driver requirements, by utilizing a novel MTBDS concept, which is controlled via a single reference electrode. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first demonstration of a switching PWM converter with such a BDS

Fig. 9. Fast Fourier Transform for the inverter voltage v_{ab} for 30 kHz (a)-(b), 60 kHz (c)-(d) and 90 kHz (e)-(f). Left column is under light load (200 W) and right column is under the nominal (850 W) load.

Fig. 10. Experimental efficiency graph for the proposed 11-level single-phase inverter.

concept. The inverters operating principles were thoroughly analyzed, and validated via simulation and a laboratory 850 W prototype.

Future work shall focus on the optimization of dead-time management and commutation, leveraging concepts such as conventional multi-step commutations found in AC-AC matrix converters [18] and more recently applied to stair-case modulated inverters [19] in order to minimize harmonic distortion and electromagnetic interference emissions. Additionally, emphasis shall be given to implement capacitor voltage balancing and voltage source reduction methods, such that the proposed MLI concept can be applied in renewable energy applications, and particularly solar.

REFERENCES

[1] International Energy Agency, "Demand: Global electricity use to grow strongly in 2025 and 2026," Jul. 2025. [Online]. Available:

<https://www.iea.org/reports/electricity-mid-year-update-2025/demand-global-electricity-use-to-grow-strongly-in-2025-and-2026>

[2] B. Srivathsan *et al.*, "AI power: Expanding data center capacity to meet growing demand," McKinsey & Company, Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/technology-media-and-telecommunications/our-insights/ai-power-expanding-data-center-capacity-to-meet-growing-demand>

[3] International Energy Agency, "Trends in electric car markets," May 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-ev-outlook-2025/trends-in-electric-car-markets-2>

[4] International Energy Agency, "Renewable electricity," Oct. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-2025/renewable-electricity>

[5] International Energy Agency, "Global renewable capacity is set to grow strongly, driven by solar PV," Oct. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/news/global-renewable-capacity-is-set-to-grow-strongly-driven-by-solar-pv>

[6] SMA Solar Technology AG, "Centralized system layout – Decentralized inverter concept," Jun. 2019, whitepaper. [Online]. Available: https://shcsystems.bg/resources/whitepaper_decentralizedsystemlayout_12.pdf

[7] ABB, "ABB's award-winning solar inverter reduces logistic and installation costs by up to 65 percent," Jun. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://new.abb.com/news/detail/5198/abbs-award-winning-solar-inverter-reduces-logistic-and-installation-costs-by-up-to-65-percent>

[8] X. Lin, D. Nam, N. Yan, J. Stewart, A. Mendes, D. Dong, R. Burgos, and D. Boroyevich, "Design and Testing of a 13.8 kV/1.1MVA 3-Phase 5-Level Flying Capacitor Converter with 10 kV SiC MOSFETs," in *2023 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)*, Mar. 2023, pp. 1839–1846.

[9] D. Zhang, J. He, and D. Pan, "A Megawatt-Scale Medium-Voltage High Efficiency High Power Density "SiC+Si" Hybrid Three-Level ANPC Inverter for Aircraft Hybrid-Electric Propulsion Systems," in *2018 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, Sep. 2018, pp. 806–813.

[10] Y. Lei, C. Barth, S. Qin, Liu *et al.*, "A 2-kW Single-Phase Seven-Level Flying Capacitor Multilevel Inverter With an Active Energy Buffer," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 8570–8581, Nov. 2017.

[11] N. C. Brooks, J. Zou, S. Coday, T. Ge, N. M. Ellis, and R. C. N. Pilawa-Podgurski, "On the Size and Weight of Passive Components: Scaling Trends for High-Density Power Converter Designs," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 8459–8477, Jul. 2024.

[12] Z. Ye, Y. Lei, W.-C. Liu, P. S. Shenoy, and R. C. N. Pilawa-Podgurski, "Improved Bootstrap Methods for Powering Floating Gate Drivers of Flying Capacitor Multilevel Converters and Hybrid Switched-Capacitor Converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 5965–5977, Jun. 2020.

[13] G. Ceglia, V. Guzman, C. Sanchez, F. Ibanez, J. Walter, and M. I. Gimenez, "A New Simplified Multilevel Inverter Topology for DC-AC Conversion," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1311–1319, Sep. 2006, 10.1109/TPEL.2006.880303.

[14] T. Moraitis and G. Kampitsis, "Static and Dynamic Characterization of a Solid-State Multi-Terminal Selector Switch," in *2025 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, Oct. 2025.

[15] J. Chen and Y. Fu, "Topology and Voltage-Balance Control of a Single-Phase Active Neutral Point Clamped Seven-Level Inverter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 6206–6210, Jun. 2021.

[16] J. Chen and C. Wang, "Topology and Voltage-Balance Control of a Single-Phase Double T-Type Seven-Level Inverter," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1075–1087, Feb. 2021.

[17] G. Carrara, S. Gardella, M. Marchesoni, R. Salutari, and G. Sciuotto, "A New Multilevel PWM Method: A Theoretical Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 497–505, Jul. 1992.

[18] P. W. Wheeler, J. Rodriguez, J. C. Clare, L. Empringham, and A. Weinstein, "Matrix Converters: A Technology Review," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 276–288, Apr. 2002.

[19] P. Adamopoulos, A. Moschopoulou, C. Apostolopoulos, G. I. Bontaitis, and G. Kampitsis, "A Novel Driving Scheme for a Multilevel Inverter Stage Utilizing a Solid-State Multi-Terminal Bidirectional Switch," in *2026 Applied Power Electronics Conference (APEC)*, Mar. 2026, in press.